

TOWARDS EFFICIENT MODULAR ADDERS BASED ON REVERSIBLE CIRCUIT

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ABSTRACT

Reversible logic is a computing paradigm that has attracted significant attention in recent years due to its properties that lead to ultra-low power and reliable circuits. Reversible circuits are fundamental, for quantum computing. Since addition is a basic operation, designing efficient adders is a cornerstone in the research of reversible circuits. Residue Number Systems (RNS) has been as a powerful to provide parallel computations where additions and multiplications are dominant. In this paper, for the first time in the literature, we propose the combination of RNS and reversible logic. The parallelism of RNS is leveraged to increase the performance of reversible computational circuits. Being the most fundamental part in any RNS, in this work we propose the implementation of modular adders, namely modulo $2n-1$ adders, using reversible logic. Analysis and comparison with traditional logic show that modulo adders can be designed using reversible gates with minimum overhead in comparison to regular adders.

1. INTRODUCTION

Researchers in academia and industry believe that Moore's law is ending, and even newly delivered deep-submicron transistors are not significantly more efficient than their previous generations. Therefore, new computing paradigms should be investigated in order to overcome the predicted

performance wall which will be reached in 2020. This rebooting of computing has to be based on novel methods at different computing levels of design abstraction, including arithmetic and circuit level, in order to address the challenges of the emerging applications such as deep convolutional neural network (DNN) and

internet-of-things (IoT). Residue Number System (RNS) is one unconventional number system that can provide fast and low-power implementation of additions and multiplications.

RNS is a different approach of dealing and representing numbers that provide parallelism at arithmetic level. This number system has been applied to achieve parallel and efficient implementations for asymmetric cryptographic and digital signal processing (DSP). RNS is used nowadays to achieve also energy-efficient and high-performance implementation of various emerging applications, such as deep neural networks, communication networks and cloud storage. However, current implementations of RNS systems, on ASICs and FPGAs, are based on the CMOS technology, which is reaching its limit. Alternative methods and technologies, such as nanoelectronic, are considered to be used. One of these alternatives is Reversible Computing (RC), which can provide ultra-low power computational circuits. In this paper, we propose the joint usage of these two unconventional computing approaches, Residue Number System and Reversible Computing, to achieve ultra-efficient computing paradigm for the emerging applications. The ability of RNS to perform

highly parallel and carry-free arithmetic is well suited for taking advantage of the features of reversible circuits. In other words, reversible logic can be efficiently used to implement RNS circuits. However, since all the available RNS structures are designed for ASIC implementation, rethinking of RNS architectures should be performed to adapt them to the properties of reversible circuits. The fundamental part of RNS systems is modular addition, since all parts of RNS including forward and reverse conversion are based on modular additions. Hence, the first step to implement RNS systems based on reversible circuits requires the design of efficient modular adders using reversible logic gates. This paper presents the first implementation of modulo $2n-1$ adders based on reversible gates. For these modular adders, which are frequently used in RNS structures parallel-prefix and ripple-carry architectures are considered.

2. EXISTING DESIGN

The first step to architect a RNS is to select a moduli set according to the target application constraints and requirements. The moduli set consists of pair-wise relatively prime numbers $\{m_1, m_2, \dots, m_n\}$, being the dynamic range the sequence of integers that can be uniquely represented in

RNS, i.e. $[0, M-1]$ with $M=m_1 \times m_2 \times \dots \times m_n$. In order to decrease the complexity of hardware realization of RNS-based arithmetic, usually near power-of-two moduli are adopted, such as $2n-1$, $2n$ and $2n+1$. Among these moduli, the simplest one to deal with is the $2n$, which does not require any specific modular arithmetic, just the circuits for binary arithmetic. Apart from that, the most frequent co-prime number in moduli sets for RNS is $2n-1$, since moduli $2n+1$ is more complex and its representation requires an additional bit. Typical RNS moduli sets are $\{2n-1, 2n+k, 2n+1\}$, $\{2n-1, 2n, 2n+1-1\}$, $\{2n-1, 2n, 2n+1, 22n+1-1\}$, $\{2k, 2n-1, 2n+1, 2n+1-1\}$ and $\{2n-1, 2n, 2n+1, 2n+1-1, 2n-1-1\}$. The main arithmetic blocks of RNS are the forward converter, the modular arithmetic in the channels, and the reverse converter. The forward converter translates the weighted binary number (X) to the residues (x_i 's), according to the moduli, as:

$$X \xrightarrow{\text{Forward Conversion}} (x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n)$$

Where

$$x_i = X \bmod m_i = |X|_{m_i} \text{ for } i = 1 \dots n$$

Note that mod indicates the remainder of integer division of X by m_i . Then, considering two numbers A and B as follows:

$$A = (a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n) \tag{3}$$

$$B = (b_1, b_2, \dots, b_n) \tag{4}$$

modulo arithmetic operations can be performed on residues as follows:

$$S = A \bullet B = (s_1, s_2, \dots, s_n)$$

where

$$s_i = |a_i \bullet b_i|_{m_i}, \bullet \in \{+, -, \times\}$$

Finally, a reverse converter maps the results in the RNS domain to the regular weighted representation, by using, for example, the Chinese remainder theorem (CRT). Other RNS operations such as sign detection, magnitude comparison and overflow handling are optional, according to the target application, and harder to perform in the RNS domain. It should be mentioned that general division cannot directly be performed in RNS, but division by a constant, one of the moduli of the set, i.e. scaling, is easier to perform.

Fig. 1. The forward converter for the moduli set $\{2n-1, 2n+k, 2n+1\}$

Most of the mentioned RNS operations are implemented using 3-to-2 carry-save adders (CSAs)

with end-around carries (EACs) and 2-to-1 modular adders. A full hardware design of RNS with moduli set $\{2n-1, 2n+k, 2n+1\}$ is reported in, and herein forward and reverse converters for this moduli set are depicted in Figs. 1 and 2, respectively. It can be observed that CSAs and carry-propagate modulo $2n-1$ adders are the components required to implement a full RNS architecture, since arithmetic in a channel also requires modulo adders and multipliers. Thus, to have an efficient modular adder is fundamental for RNS-based applications.

Fig 2. The full reverse converter for the moduli set $\{2n-1, 2n+k, 2n+1\}$.

The CSA with EAC consists of independent full adders (FAs) which just combine the three inputs into two carry-save output vectors, as shown in Fig. 3. Its delay is just the delay of a single FA, while the overall area linearly depends on the width of the operands

Fig. 3. The 4-bit CSA with EAC structure.

Note that CSA with CEAC is similar to CSA with EAC, just the end-around carry is complemented. Modular carry propagate adders can be designed based on different architectures, from low-cost ripple-carry adders (RCAs) (Fig. 4) to fast parallel-prefix adders (PPAs). The

PPAs architectures can provide a good trade-off between circuit's parameters, being popular in RNS arithmetic circuits.

Fig 4. The 4-bit modulo $2n-1$ adder based on ripple-carry method, namely RCA with EAC.

3. PROPOSED DESIGN

MOTIVATION BEHIND REVERSIBLE LOGIC

High-performance chips releasing large amounts of heat impose practical limitation on how far can we improve the performance of the system. Reversible circuits that conserve information, by uncomputing bits instead of throwing them away, will soon offer the only physically possible way to

keep improving performance. Reversible computing will also lead to improvement in energy efficiency. Energy efficiency will fundamentally affect the speed of circuits such as nanocircuits and therefore the speed of most computing applications. To increase the portability of devices again reversible computing is required. It will let circuit element sizes to reduce to atomic size limits and hence devices will become more portable. Although the hardware design costs incurred in near future may be high but the power cost and performance being more dominant than logic hardware cost in today's computing era, the need of reversible

REVERSIBLE GATES

Reversible circuits provide a one-to-one relation between inputs and outputs, therefore inputs can be recovered from outputs. This interesting feature results in significant power saving in digital circuits. Classical digital gates are not reversible, reversible gates should be designed as basic components to design logical reversible circuits. Well known reversible gates are Feynman, Peres and HNG. The Feynman or controlled not (CNOT) gate is frequently used in reversible circuits, since it can

provide exclusive OR (XOR) as well as copy and complement of the input.

Since reversible circuits do not take advantage of fan-out, this gate can be used to achieve two copies of the same input by setting the other input of the gate to the zero-logic level. Similarly, by setting the second input of the CNOT to one-logic level, we can achieve the complement of the other input.

1 Feynman Gate

- Feynman gate is a 2*2 one through reversible gate as shown in figure 1.
- The input vector is $I(A, B)$ and the output vector is $O(P, Q)$.
- The outputs are defined by $P=A, Q=A \text{ xor } B$. Quantum cost of a Feynman gate is 1.
- Feynman Gate (FG) can be used as a copying gate. Since a fan-out is not allowed in reversible logic, this gate is useful for duplication of the required outputs.

Figure 1: Feynman Gate

A	B	P	Q
0	0	0	0
0	1	0	1
1	0	1	1
1	1	1	0

Table 1: Truth table of Feynman gates

2 Double Feynman Gate (F2G)

- Fig.2 shows a 3*3 Double Feynman gate.
- The input vector is I (A, B, C) and the output vector is O (P, Q, R). The outputs are
- defined by $P = A$, $Q=A \text{ xor } B$, $R=A \text{ xor } C$.
- Quantum cost of double Feynman gate is 2.

Fig 2: Double Feynman gate

A	B	C	P	Q	R
0	0	0	0	0	0
0	0	1	0	0	1
0	1	0	0	1	0
0	1	1	0	1	1
1	0	0	1	1	1
1	0	1	1	1	0
1	1	0	1	0	1
1	1	1	1	0	0

Table 2: Truth table of double Feynman gates

3 Toffoli Gate:

- Fig 3 shows a 3*3 Toffoli gate.
- The input vector is I (A, B, C) and the output vector is O(P,Q,R).
- The outputs are defined by $P=A$, $Q=B$, $R=AB \text{ xor } C$.
- Quantum cost of a Toffoli gate is 5.

Fig 3: Toffoli gate

A	B	C	P	Q	R
0	0	0	0	0	0
0	0	1	0	0	1
0	1	0	0	1	0
0	1	1	0	1	1
1	0	0	1	0	0
1	0	1	1	0	1
1	1	0	1	1	1
1	1	1	1	1	0

Table 3: Truth table of Toffoli gate

4 Fredkin Gate

- Fig 4 shows a 3*3 Fredkin gate.
- The input vector is I (A, B, C) and the output vector is O (P, Q, R).
- The output is defined by P=A, Q=A'B⊕AC and R=A'C⊕AB.
- Quantumcost of a Fredkin gate is 5.

Fig 4: Fredkin gate

A	B	C	P	Q	R
0	0	0	0	0	0
0	0	1	0	0	1
0	1	0	0	1	0
0	1	1	0	1	1
1	0	0	1	0	0
1	0	1	1	0	1
1	1	0	1	0	1
1	1	1	1	1	1

Table 4: Truth table of fredkin gate

5 Peres Gate

- Fig 5 shows a 3*3 Peres gate.
- The input vector is I(A, B, C) and the output vector is O (P, Q, R).
- The output is defined by P = A, Q = A xor B and R=AB xor C.
- Quantum cost of a Peres gate is 4.
- In the proposed design Peres gate is used because of its lowest quantum cost.

Fig 5: Peres gate

A	B	C	P	Q	R
0	0	0	0	0	0
0	0	1	0	0	1
0	1	0	0	1	0
0	1	1	0	1	1
1	0	0	1	1	0
1	0	1	1	1	1
1	1	0	1	0	1
1	1	1	1	0	0

Table 5: Truth table of peres gate

- Fig 7 shows a 4*4 TSG gate.
- The input vector is I (A,B, C, D) and the output vector is O (P, Q, R, S).
- The output is defined by $P = A$, $Q = A'C'xorB'$, $R = (A'C'xorB')xor D$ and
- $S = (A'C'xorB').Dxor (ABxorC)$.
- Quantum cost of a Peres gate is 4.
- In the proposed design Peres gate is used because of its lowest quantum cost.
- It can be verified that the input pattern corresponding to a particular output pattern can be
- uniquely determined.
- The proposed TSG gate is capable of implementing all Boolean functions and can also
- work singly as a reversible Full adder.

Fig 7 TSG gate

Fig 8 TSG Gate Working As Reversible Full Adder

7 Sayem gate

- SG is a 1 trough 4x4 reversible gate.

- The input and output vector of this gate are, $I_v = (A, B, C, D)$ and
- $O_v = (A, A'B xor AC, A'B xor AC xor D, AB xor A'C xor D)$.
- The block diagram of this gate is shown in Fig .

The CSA with EAC

The CSA is a 3-to-2 compression unit that is very popular for regular arithmetic as well as in RNS architectures due to its speed and cost. According to Fig. 3, a CSA can be built by using n FAs for adding three n-bit operands. According to, the HNG reversible gate can be used to realize a FA by setting the fourth input of HNG to the zero-logic level, as shown in Fig. 6.

Fig. 6. The CSA with EAC using HNG reversible gates.

The quantum depth and cost of a HNG gate is 5Δ and 6, respectively. Therefore, the total quantum depth and cost of a n-bit CSA with EAC will be 5Δ and $6n$, respectively, since the delay of a CSA is equal to the delay of just one FA. Besides, the final reversible circuits will have n constant inputs and $2n$ garbage outputs.

The RCA-based Modulo Adder

As shown in Fig. 4, the RCA with EAC for modulo $2n-1$ addition of two n -bit numbers, requires n FAs and n HAs in the first and second levels, respectively. Similar to CSA, FAs can be realized with HNG gates. Besides, the Peres reversible gate can be used to implement a HA, where the third input bit is set to zero, as shown in Fig. 7. The final quantum cost of the RCA with EAC for two n -bit operands is $6n+4n=10n$, since the individual quantum cost and depth of a Peres gate is 4. Besides, the total quantum depth of the RCA with EAC is $((3 \times (n-1) + 4 + (3 \times (n-1) + 5)) \Delta$. Furthermore, the total constant inputs and garbage outputs are $2n$ and $3n$, respectively since one of the inputs of HNG and Peres gates is zero, and also two and one outputs of HNG and Peres gates, respectively, are not used.

Fig. 7. The RCA with EAC using HNG and Peres reversible gates.

Brent-Kung Adder

Brent-kung adder is one of the parallel prefix adders used for speeding of the operation. Parallel prefix adders are the fast adders and perform the arithmetic operations at the fast rate. Most Industries are using parallel prefix adders because of their advantages compare to other adders. Parallel prefix adders are faster and area efficient. Parallel prefix adder is a technique for increasing the speed in DSP processor while performing addition. The Brent-Kung adder was developed by Brent and Kung which they published in 1982. Brent-Kung has maximum logic depth and minimum area. The number of cells is calculated by using $2(n-1) - \log_2 n$. The 4-bit and 32 bit Brent- Kung adder figures shown below. Brent Kung adder is one of the parallel prefix adders. It is the most popular adder that is used to increase the speed of operation. These adders are designed by using carry look ahead adders structure.

4.RESULTS

RTL SCHEMATIC:it stands for register transfer level (RTL) and is a blueprint of an architectural design used to verify that it matches our ideal design. To turn a description of the architecture into a functioning summary, verilog or vhdl is needed. There are also internal connection blocks that are included in the RTL design

for easier debugging The RTL schematic diagram for the planned architecture is shown in the image below.

Fig :RTL Schematic view existed design

Fig :RTL Schematic of proposed design

TECHNOLOGY SCHEMATIC:- The technology schematic makes the representation of the architecture in the LUT format, where the LUT is considered as the parameter of area that is used in VLSI to estimate the architecture design. The LUT is considered as a square unit; the memory allocation of the code is represented in these LUTs in FPGA.

Fig :View technology schematic of existed design

Fig: View technology schematic of proposed design Simulation

The simulation is the process which is termed as the final verification in respect to its working where as the schematic is the verification of the connections and blocks. The simulation window is launched as shifting from implementation to the simulation on the home screen of the tool, and the simulation window confines the output in the form of wave forms output.

Here it has the flexibility of providing the different radix number systems.

Fig : simulated wave forms of existed design

Fig: family selected for synthesis

Fig : simulated wave forms of proposed design

PARAMETERS:-

Consider in VLSI the parameters treated are area ,delay ,frequency and power ,based on these parameters one can judge the one architecture to other. here the consideration of area considered the parameters are obtained by using the tool XILINX 14.7 and the HDL is verilog language .

Parameter	modulo adder with logic gates	modulo adder with reversible logic gates
No of LUTs	124	64

Table7.1 : Parameter comparison table

Fig: LUT comparison bar graph

5. CONCLUSIONS

In this project, the proposed modular adder using reversible logic gates and bruntkung adder better than the existing modular adder using logic gates and koggestone adder. From the table 7.1 the proposed design uses less LUTs 64 when compared with the existing design with an LUTs count of 124. those are shown in table7.1. This work presents the reversible design of modular adders working on residue number system, a basic and fundamental element of RNS- based architectures. It is shown that a modulo $2n-1$ parallel-prefix adder can be designed using small overheads over regular prefix adders.

6. REFERENCES

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